

PREDICTING LOCAL STRAINS IN TEXTILE COMPOSITES USING THE BINARY MODEL FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

The Binary Model has established itself a computationally efficient and highly adaptable approach to analyzing diverse forms of textile composites, including 3D weaves and braids, integral structures, stitched components, and knitted fabrics. Early work demonstrated that the Binary Model gives an accurate account of the global stiffness of textiles with complex 3D reinforcement architecture. Axial and shear properties and Poisson's ratios are estimated quite accurately, provided correct information about the total fiber count and orientation is available. Moreover, solutions to the problem of stiffness knockdown due to tow waviness can easily be found directly by offsetting tow nodes to introduce the measured degree of waviness. While the utility of the Binary Model formulation for *global* stiffness estimation has been established, the question of the degree of fidelity that can be attained in predicting *local* strain variations associated with details of the tow architecture remains unresolved. In particular, the nature of the Binary Model formulation leads to the concern that predicted local strains will be strongly mesh dependent.

This study addresses this concern of mesh dependence in the Binary Model. Motivated by recent proposals that a strain measure averaged over some gauge length will prove out as the best predictor of failure for most failure mechanisms observed in textile composites, this study seeks to define a range of gauge lengths over which the Binary Model gives mesh-independent, spatially averaged strains. Full-field strain measurements of a carbon fibre/SiC matrix composite in which the reinforcement is a 3D angle-interlock weave are used to validate the local strain predictions made by the generalized Binary Model.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Binary Model (BM) was introduced some years ago as a computationally efficient and highly adaptable approach to analyzing diverse forms of textile composites, including 3D weaves and braids, integral structures, stitched components, and knitted fabrics [1-4]. Over the past several years, the Binary Model has established itself a computationally efficient and highly adaptable approach to analyzing diverse forms of textile composites, including 3D weaves and braids, integral structures, stitched components, and knitted fabrics. Early work demonstrated that the Binary Model gives an accurate account of the global stiffness of textiles with complex 3D reinforcement architecture. Axial and shear properties and Poisson's ratios are estimated quite accurately, provided correct information about the total fiber count and orientation is available. Moreover, solutions to the problem of stiffness knockdown due to tow waviness can easily be found directly by offsetting tow nodes to introduce the measured degree of waviness.

While the utility of the Binary Model formulation for *global* stiffness estimation has been established, the question of the degree of fidelity that can be attained in predicting *local* strain variations associated with details of the tow architecture remains unresolved. In particular, the nature of the Binary

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Model formulation leads to the concern that predicted local strains will be strongly mesh dependent. This is because in the BM formulation the tow architecture is represented geometrically by a set of 1D line elements, which identify the location in 3D space of the axes of all the tows in the textile. The 1D elements is embedded in a set of conventional 3D solid finite elements called effective medium elements, which models the entire composite structure. In terms of mechanics, the 1D elements represent the axial properties of the tows (axial stiffness, axial thermal conductivity, axial thermal expansion) while the 3D elements represent the matrix-dominated properties of the composite (transverse stiffness, shear stiffness, Poisson's effect, transverse thermal conductivity, transverse thermal expansion). The possibility of strong mesh dependence arises in the Binary Model from the use of 1D elements; i.e., the representation of an entity with non-zero cross-section by an element with zero cross-section. If 1D elements were placed in an elastic continuum (with infinite degrees of freedom), they would exhibit a divergent response: non-zero displacements would occur for vanishing applied loads. A finite response is observed in the Binary Model because the effective medium has limited degrees of freedom. The effective medium mesh is usually defined to have a size similar to the tow spacing. Since the strain fields around a tow element node are therefore averaged (by the numerical formulation of the finite element method) over volumes commensurate with the effective medium mesh, the divergent response is effectively integrated out to some finite, average response of a nonzero volume of material. However, the nature of the averaging is an arbitrary function of the mesh choice; and therefore the absolute values of the predicted local strain fields are of questionable significance.

While mesh refinement can in principle remove singularities due to the 1D character of the tow elements in the Binary Model formulation, a second source of singularities (or numerically smoothed vestiges of singularities) will still remain. This second source of singularities is the material mismatch between the effective medium (or inter-tow material) and the tows themselves. In other approaches to the analysis of textile composites, this source of singularity is sometimes treated in great detail. To reveal the details, careful attention must be paid to the exact description of the geometry of the interface between the dissimilar phases of the composite; the local geometry, along with the elastic mismatch, controls the singular behaviour. Once the details of strain or stress concentrations have been computed, fracture mechanics can be invoked in an attempt to predict failure initiation at the site of a singularity.

In our view, this level of detail in failure analysis is inappropriate in the face of the reality of textile composites in engineering practice. First, textiles always contain a significant degree of irregularity on the scale of individual tows, mainly because of the imperfection of the textile process. Therefore, the strain or stress concentrations that arise in the finished composite will show strong stochastic variations, which will always be very difficult to quantify. Second, the mechanisms of failure that are most commonly seen in a polymeric textile composite, viz., matrix cracking, local delamination, shear failures, tow kinking in compression, and tow rupture in tension, are not generally associated with a point value of stress or the strength of a stress or strain concentration. Instead, they are governed by some measure of the strain (or stress) averaged over some spatial gauge length (or volume). Elsewhere, evidence for this claim is surveyed and arguments concerning the micromechanics of local failure events are used to suggest that the relevant gauge length should be the width of a single tow [8].

This study addresses this concern of mesh dependence in the Binary Model. Motivated by recent proposals that a strain measure averaged over some gauge length will prove out as the best predictor of failure for most failure mechanisms observed in textile composites, this study seeks to define a range of gauge lengths over which the Binary Model gives mesh-independent, spatially averaged strains. Full-field strain measurements of a carbon fibre/SiC matrix composite in which the reinforcement is a 3D angle-interlock weave are used to validate the local strain predictions made by the generalized Binary Model.

2. AVERAGING SCHEME

A representative volume or cell containing a single tow crossover is chosen for the averaging scheme used for validating the local strain prediction of the 3D angle interlock composite. Such a crossover could be found in a plain woven or 2D braided fabric and is similar geometrically to strain concentrating features in 3D weaves or braids. The composite represented by the cell, consisting of solid tows (tows of nonzero section) in a matrix with well-defined tow/matrix interface geometry, will be termed the model composite. This composite is to be approximated by the Binary Model, with 1D tow elements embedded in effective medium elements.

The cell is cuboidal, with dimensions 10 x 10 x 2 mm in the coordinate system (x, y, z) (Fig. 1). The tows in the model composite consist of piece-wise homogeneous, rectangular prismatic segments as shown in Fig. 1a. The tows occupy approximately 50% of the volume of the cell. The section of a tow formed by any plane of constant x_1 (for the tow parallel to x_1) or x_2 (for the tow parallel to x_2) is a rectangle of dimensions 5 x 1 mm. The tows in the model composite are transversely isotropic, with the axis of isotropy along the tow axis. The remaining volume of the cell is isotropic. The mesh for the model composite is shown in Fig. 1b. The tow shapes have been simplified into saw-tooth loci. A uniform strain of 1% was applied at the surface of $x = 10$, while periodic condition were imposed on the surface of $y = 0$, and $y = 10$. The Binary Model calculations were executed by ABAQUS (V6.2) and the method of multi-point constraints was invoked by using the “embedded element” function.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of the model composite, containing a single tow crossover (not to scale), and (b) Binary Model meshes and averaging box.

A post-processing subroutine was developed to read strain data from the ABAQUS output data file (*.dat) and calculate strains averaged over a specified gauge length. The spatially averaged strain at a point \otimes was computed by integrating the Binary Model strains numerically over a cuboidal volume of dimensions $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$, which was centred on \otimes . The point \otimes was moved along the line $(x = 5, z = 1)$ with a small incremental step. At each step, the strain component to be averaged was evaluated by interpolation from the nodal values given by the Binary Model at n^3 locations within the averaging volume, indicated by the black dots in Fig. 1b. The mean of these n^3 values was taken to be the averaged value at \otimes . Where some part of the averaging volume lies beyond the cell, the values on the cell boundary are used and the averaging volume is truncated. Defining a sufficiently large value of n and an appropriate averaging volume, $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$, are two of the major objectives of the study.

For all averaging volumes, $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$, within the range of interest, the computed spatially averaged strains converged with increasing n at $n \geq 7$, even though the integration scheme used is only first order (errors linear in n). Figure 2a illustrates convergence for $n = 3, 7$, or 9 and an averaging volume of $2.5 \times 2.5 \times 1$ mm. The raw (non-averaged) output of the Binary Model is also shown so that the magnitude of variations with choice of n can be compared with the shifts due to the averaging step. Figure 2b compares the strain components, ϵ_x , ϵ_y , and ϵ_z , as predicted by the Binary Model using the meshes shown in Fig. 1 with the same strain fields subjected to spatial averaging using different averaging volumes. It clearly shows that the spatially-averaged strains converge to the raw Binary Model results as the averaging volume decreases. When the averaging volume becomes large, information about local strain fluctuation characteristics is lost and the averaged strains converge to the macroscopic predictions found from homogenized composite mechanics. Between the small and large limits, an averaging volume exists that retains the local strain variation characteristics yet provides relatively mesh independent results. Further numerical investigation shows that strains predicted by the Binary Model that have been averaged over a volume whose linear dimensions *exceed* half the cross-sectional (width) dimensions of a tow are reasonably mesh-independent [9]. However, this conclusion has yet to be validated through direct comparisons between predictions and experimental measurements, which is given in the next section.

Figure 2. (a) Convergence with increasing number n^3 of integration points for calculating spatially averaged strains; (b) Averaged strains converge to BM raw data as averaging box size decreases.

3. VALIDATED PREDICTIONS OF A 3D C/SiC WEAVE

BM Setup – The subject of this validation study is a thin composite sheet (~ 1 mm thick) consisting of a 3D angle interlock reinforcement of T300² carbon fibers in a SiC matrix. This composite has been developed over the last few years for applications in heat exchangers. The focus of this study is to demonstrate the capability of the Binary Model in predicting the local strain variations at the scale of a fiber tow, as well as the global elasticity. A representative cell was analyzed for each composite, for which periodic boundary conditions were assumed, although it is not necessary in Binary Model simulations to assume periodicity in either the structure or the stress and strain fields. The representative cells for the two composites are marked by white lines in Fig. 3a. Each tow in the interlock pattern was

² Thornel® Carbon Fiber T-300, Amoco Performance Products, Inc., Atlanta, GA.

represented by a single string of one-dimensional (1D) elements (“tow elements”) that followed a piecewise linear wave pattern with a trapezoidal shape (Fig. 3b).

Figure 3 (a) Top surface and sections normal to the warp (horizontal) and weft (vertical) directions of the C/SiC composite, (b) The tow element meshes used to simulate the composite, which showing piecewise linear approximations of sinusoidal tow paths. The blue lines represent weft tows, the red lines represent warp tows, and the green mesh outlines 3D effective medium elements.

BM Predicted And Measured Strain Maps —Strain fields were measured using laser speckle interferometry for the composite loaded in uniaxial tension in the weft direction. Since in this composite, the weft tows are wavy (Fig 3) and this leads to strong spatial variations in the strain field. Figure 4 compares the measured and predicted fields of the aligned and transverse components of strain, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , where, in the global coordinate system, (x_1, x_2, x_3) , x_1 is aligned with the load (vertical direction in figure) and x_2 is the transverse direction. The measured strain fields, which are those seen on the top surface of the composite, cover most of the tested gauge section. The measured strains have been plotted as relative strains, defined as the strain value divided by the average value over the whole gauge section. The predicted fields have been built up over a similar region by joining together replicas of the fields calculated for a single unit cell. Both ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 show strong spatial variations.

Figure 4 shows that the Binary Model has reproduced all the qualitative variations that are observed experimentally. The measured aligned strain, ϵ_1 , shows intense red lines in a periodic pattern. These are in fact cracks that occur where a weft tow passes beneath a warp tow [7]. While the simulation in Fig. 4 was restricted to elastic behaviour (no failure criterion considered), one notes that the cracks coincide in position with the peak predicted values of ϵ_1 . The small patches of relatively low strain, i.e., the blue dots in Fig. 3b (experiment), are at least suggested in their location by corresponding green dots in Fig. 4a (prediction). Comparison of the magnitude of the strains in regions of high strain (but away from the cracks) or regions of low strain suggests agreement between experiment and theory, but the details depend on the spatial averaging that has been used in the model and in the analysis of experimental data.

The experimentally measured transverse strain, ϵ_2 , shows an unusual feature that is peculiar to the 3D nature of the textile architecture: regions of contraction (positive relative strain) alternate with regions of dilation (negative relative strain). The alternating pattern arises from local bending of the skin by the

action of the warp weaver (or through-thickness) tows. An intuitive description of the effect is as follows. Each warp weaver tends to straighten under applied tension or become more wavy under compression. Since the pattern of warp weavers varies in phase across the laminate, the warp weavers create an alternating bending moment in the laminate. Under tension, material near the turning point of one warp weaver on the outer surface of the laminate will be pulled into the laminate, while neighbouring material, which lies above a turning point of the opposite sense in another warp weaver on the other side of the laminate, will be pushed up. Under compression, the opposite deformation will occur. The alternating bending effects cause the alternation of the transverse strains. This effect would probably not be visible (above the average Poisson's effect) in a thicker laminate.

Strains Averaged over Gauges—Quantitative comparisons of predicted and measured local strain variations are more conveniently visualized on line scans. Figure 5 shows scans along the lines indicated by dotted lines in Fig. 4. The component of strain aligned with the load, ε_1 , and the transverse component of strain, ε_2 , are shown. Both the experimental and predicted data have been averaged over gauges. In the case of the experimental data, the average is taken along a line interval of length l_{av} in the direction of the scan line (x_2 -direction). No averaging is done in the loading direction (x_1 -direction), except the averaging implicit in the pixel size of the data set. In the case of the simulations, the average was taken over a solid volume of dimensions l_{av} in the scan direction, 0.04 mm in the loading direction (the dimension of a single pixel), and 0.01 mm in the direction into the material (x_3 -direction). The last dimension was chosen to be small since the data are surface measurements. In averaging strains for failure criteria, a gauge volume with larger dimensions in the x_1 and x_2 directions, e.g., comparable to the tow width, would be preferred.

The three values of l_{av} used in Fig. 4 are 0.24, 0.48, and 0.96 mm, which correspond to one quarter, one half, and one whole width of a warp tow in the x_2 -direction. Predictions are shown for $E_{eff} = 15$ GPa (elastic matrix) and $E_{eff} = 7.5$ GPa. The reduced value of E_{eff} (arbitrarily chosen) indicates the possible effect of matrix microcracking. As in Fig. 3, the strains have been normalized against the average far-field values and their average is therefore unity.

As the gauge length, l_{av} , increases, noise in the experimental data and mesh-dependent, rapid variations in the predictions (more pronounced for smaller averaging gauge lengths than shown in Fig. 3 [9]) both diminish. For $l_{av} \geq 0.48$ mm (half the tow width), the average of the strain and the periodic character of the strain variation are fairly well reproduced for both strain components. However, for calculations performed with the value $E_{eff} = 15$ GPa, corresponding to an elastic matrix, the amplitude of the periodic variation is under-predicted. For example, the peak in the predicted transverse strain lies near zero strain, rather than becoming positive. The calculations using $E_{eff} = 7.5$ indicate the order of magnitude changes that might be expected when the modulus is reduced by microcracking (Fig. 3). The agreement with experiment improves as the modulus is reduced, but is not perfected. Nevertheless, the degree of agreement between experiment and theory is reasonable, given the uncertainty in the data due to measurement errors or imperfect characterization of the base material constitutive properties.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 Comparison of predicted (left) and measured (right) fields of (a) aligned strain, ϵ_1 , and (b) transverse strain, ϵ_2 , for composite H loaded in uniaxial tension in the x_1 -direction (weft direction – indicated by arrows).

Figure 5 Comparison of predicted (solid) and measured (dashed) relative strains for averaging gauge lengths $L_y =$ (a) 0.24, (b) 0.48, and (c) 0.96 mm (quarter, half, and whole tow width). In each of (a), (b), and (c), the top figure shows the aligned strain, ϵ_1 , and the bottom figure the transverse strain, ϵ_2 , along the scan lines indicated in Figure 4. The effective medium modulus is indicated in the legends. BM = Binary Model.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Binary Model has been demonstrated by experimental validation to predict the effects of textile architecture on local strain variations acceptably well, when strains are averaged over gauge lengths greater than or equal to one tow half-width. The strain variations include strong oscillations in the transverse strain, which is an essentially textile phenomenon – no analogue exists in laminated composites.

The predicted strain fluctuations occur on the scale of individual reinforcing tows. This is the same scale as that on which local failure mechanisms, including microcracking, tensile tow rupture, and tow kinking (compressive failure) occur [10,11]. These mechanisms cause thermal and structural nonlinearities and often lead to ultimate failure.

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